

Evidence of a dynamically evolving Galactic warp

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The Galactic disc exhibits a large-scale distortion of the outer parts with respect to the inner parts [1], commonly known as *the Galactic warp* (Figure 1). While numerous models have been proposed to explain its origin and dynamical nature (including intergalactic magnetic fields [2], a misaligned infall of gas [3], the influence of a satellite galaxy [4], a torque from the dark matter halo of the Galaxy [5]), which mechanism is actually at work remains unclear. Thanks to the unparalleled wealth of astrometric information from the Gaia satellite [6, 7, 8, 9], stellar kinematics in the Galactic disc can be analysed, with the aim of constraining the warp's dynamical nature.

Figure 1: The structure of our Galaxy, the Milky Way, with its warped galactic disc. This figure has been created for the ESA press release of the paper presented here [10]. Credit: Stefan Payne-Wardenaar; Inset: NASA/JPL-Caltech; Layout: ESA. ESA press release: https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Space_Science/Gaia/Milky_Way_s_warp_caused_by_galactic_collision_Gaia_suggests.

The temporal evolution of the Galactic warp

Using the collisionless Boltzmann equation, a simple model of how the warp orientation changes with time can be constructed. In general, the modelled warp can vary its amplitude and line-of-nodes (see Figure 2 and animated version, details in [10]) as a function of time. Depending on the magnitude and direction of such variations, different signatures are expected in the present-day vertical velocities of stars. When the warp figure is frozen in time, and only the line-of-nodes is changing its azimuthal angle, the kinematic signature manifests itself as systematic vertical velocities along the line-of-nodes toward the outer parts of the disc. The variation of the warp line-of-nodes is sometimes called in the literature warp *precession* (or warp angular speed), and we therefore call this model the *long-lived precessing warp*. If we, instead, set to zero all temporal variations, we obtain the so-called *static* warp model. Taking advantage of *Gaia* data, it is now possible to tackle outstanding ques-

tions about how (and if) the warp is evolving as a function of time. As discussed in the following, observational constraints on the warp kinematics would be particularly useful to learn more about the evolutionary history of the Galactic disc.

Figure 2: Three-dimensional representation of the precessing warp model. The Sun's position is shown by the dot, the Galactic Centre by the black cross and the direction of Galactic rotation by the arrow. The angle between the warp's line of nodes (bold solid line) and the Sun's azimuth ($\phi = 0^\circ$, dashed line) is the warp phase angle at the present time. Taken from Fig. 2 of ref. [10]. An animated version is available in Supplementary Video 1 of ref. [10].

Measuring the warp precession

Using astrometric information from Gaia Data Release 2 [8] for 12 million giant stars (details on the sample in [11]), together with a model for the structure and kinematics of the Galactic disc (including the above-discussed warp model), astrometric uncertainties and survey selection function, we measured the warp precession rate. For a given set of parameters, the estimated value of warp precession is degenerate with some of the assumed parameters, e.g., the mean azimuthal stellar velocity, the assumed parallax zero-point for Gaia data [12], and the assumed warp amplitude. For this reason, we tested several values of these parameters available in the literature. Specifically, for the warp amplitude, we explored spatial geometries from [13], which [14] found in good agreement with their distribution of RGB (red giant branch) stars, a stellar population similar to the one we adopted; we also used the model from [15] based on red-clump stars at $R \lesssim 13$ kpc (according to the spatial limitation of that model); we tested the parametrisations from [16],

based on 2MASS star counts, and the stellar model from [17]. Additionally, we tested the geometry from [18] based on Cepheids, a stellar population different from the one we adopted, but for which precise distance estimates can be obtained. Indeed, the geometry of the Galactic warp is quite uncertain for several reasons: part of this uncertainty comes from the fact that different stellar populations might have intrinsically different amplitudes, and part is due to the different techniques used to derive distance estimates/reconstruct the three-dimensional distribution of stars in the Galaxy (which can imply different results even for the same stellar population). According to all the geometric parametrisations tested above, the estimated warp precession is significantly different from zero (thus in disagreement with the static warp model). The final measurement that we report for the warp precession is 10.86 ± 0.03 (stat) ± 3.20 (syst) $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{kpc}^{-1}$ in the direction of Galactic rotation, about one-third the angular rotation velocity at the Sun's position in the Galaxy. Recently, [19] obtained a consistent value of $13.57^{+0.20}_{-0.18} \text{km s}^{-1} \text{kpc}^{-1}$ using Starhorse distances [20], supporting the scenario of a significantly prograde warp precession.

Implications

The Galactic disc is a complex structure, whose evolution is driven by several evolutionary processes. Signatures in the structure and kinematics of the Galactic disc can be left by both internal (e.g., secular evolution processes) and external (e.g., interaction with satellite galaxies) mechanisms. In this context, observational constraints play a fundamental role, as they can shed light on the possible scenarios available to date, and help us to better understand the evolutionary history of our own Galaxy. Using N-body simulations of a Milky Way-like galaxy [21], we analysed the response of the Galactic disc to the repeated impacts of a satellite galaxy (whose properties are similar to the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy, commonly considered as one of the major perturbers of the Galactic disc). We find that a significantly prograde warp precession rate is a natural consequence of an interaction with a satellite, giving a possible interpretation to the measurements presented in [10, 19]. On the other hand, in the semi-quiescent phases, the warp precession is close to zero (which, according to the model presented above, would be more consistent with the static case).

The experiment performed with N-body simulations suggests that the warp precession rate can be an important parameter, whose measurement, in the context of a Milky Way-satellite system, has a constraining power on the dynamical state of interaction [22].

Limitations and future prospects

The simple model presented here only represents a first step toward our understanding of the disc's dynamical evolution. For example, it would be interesting to explore more sophisticated models including differential precession and/or additional Fourier vertical distortions (e.g., the azimuthal term $m = 2$). Moreover, future data-sets from the Gaia satellite and other ground-based surveys will presumably shed further light on the warp precession, being based on more precise astrometric measurements, covering larger portions of the Galactic disc, and providing additional information for stellar astrophysical parameters. We are living in the Golden Age of Galactic studies: present and future data-sets, combined with more realistic models, will surely reveal key information on the evolutionary history of the Galactic disc, and the role played by its environment.

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